

COST AND INCOME ANALYSIS OF ORGANIC FARMING UNDER *PARAMPARAGAT KRISHI VIKAS YOJNA* (PKVY) IN SRI GANGANAGAR DISTRICT OF RAJASTHANVijender Kumar^{1*}, Madhu Sharma², Priyanka Yadav¹, Sanskaran Swami³ and Shobhana Bishnoi⁴¹Department of Agricultural Economics and Management, Rajasthan College of Agriculture, MPUAT, Udaipur, Rajasthan, India²Department of Agricultural Economics, College of Agriculture, SKRAU, Bikaner, Rajasthan, India³Department of Agricultural Extension and Communication, College of Agriculture, SKRAU, Bikaner, Rajasthan, India⁴Department of Agricultural Economics, College of Agriculture, SKNAU, Jobner (Rajasthan), India*Corresponding email: vijenderkumar198@gmail.com

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Abstract

A field survey was conducted on farmers of Sri Ganganagar District to understand the PKVY scheme and to assess its impact on farmers' income. Multistage sampling technique was used for selecting 80 beneficiary farmers of PKVY and 80 non-beneficiary farmers from four randomly selected tehsils and 8 randomly selected villages. Returns were calculated over variable cost to study the impact of organic farming on costs and returns. Total cost of cultivation of the moong bean crop for beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers was ₹ 26518.76 per hectare and ₹ 23479.19 per hectare, respectively. In rabi season, beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers incurred a total cost of cultivation of ₹ 28468.24 and ₹ 31390.63 per hectare for the Wheat crop respectively. The benefit-cost ratio (BCR) of the moong bean crop for beneficiary farmers was 1.44 which was found lower as compared to BCR of non-beneficiary farmers i.e., 2.28. The benefit-cost ratio (BCR) of the wheat crop for beneficiary farmers was 2.94 which was found higher as compared to BCR of non-beneficiary farmers i.e., 2.49.

Keywords: PKVY, Returns, Variable cost, BCR.**Introduction**

It is an undeniably truth that Agriculture is the foundation of the Indian Economy. Today, India positions second worldwide in crop production. Farming and allied sectors represented 16.38 percent of the GDP in 2021 (Ministry of Statistics and Program Implementation, 2021), utilized 41.49 percent of the total labour force (Plecher, 2020). In spite of a consistent decrease of its share in the GDP, it is yet the biggest economical area and plays a vital role in the all-round socio-economic growth of India. After independence, India faced a serious food crisis.

The green revolution was the turning point in Indian agriculture. Within 10 years of green revolution, India totally stopped food imports from abroad. In spite of the benefits gained by India in terms of achieving self-sufficiency in food production and expanding livelihood choices rural poor, green revolution made Indian farmers and rest of the world to depend mostly on chemical fertilizers and pesticides, which deteriorated the soil fertility and environment drastically.

Toxic chemicals used in conventional agriculture have also penetrated into our food chain (Committee on Estimates, 2015-16). Organic farming, on the other hand, is more environmentally safe than conventional farming systems. Organic farming systems have greater soil carbon levels, higher moisture retention, better soil quality and less soil erosion (Sharma et al. 2015). Organic farming contains no risk of synthetic pesticide pollution of ground and surface waters (Reganold and Wachter, 2016).

Looking at the benefits of organic farming and to sustain soil health and food security, India has started many programmes to promote organic farming. Among these programmes, the PKVY Scheme was launched by the NDA (National Democratic Alliance) government in the year 2016-17 to bring 5 lakh acres under organic farming by 10,000 organic clusters. This centrally sponsored scheme is being implemented by the state government for the farmers. For the financial year 2016-17, a combined sum of ₹ 412 crores has been allocated for the schemes, 'PKVY' and 'Organic Value Chain Development in North East Region'. A study from southern Rajasthan shows that the net returns per hectare received from organic farming were relatively higher or good enough as compared to conventional farming (Singh et al. 2023). To promote organic farming, there is a need to incentivise and promote the adoption of organic farming practices among the farmers (Ranwa et al. 2024). From the previous research findings, crops respond better to organic management, particularly after an initial conversion period of 2-3 years in rainfed areas. Thus, Organic farming can significantly contribute to improving the livelihoods of smallholders as it can generate net higher incomes and involves less risk than inorganic farming (Gopinath et al. 2025).

The present study was undertaken with the following objectives:

- Use of inputs by beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries of PKVY
- Difference in cost of cultivation
- Difference in gross and net returns
- Difference in marketing channels to sell the outputs and price of outputs

Research methodology

Multi-stage sampling technique was used for the selection of sample farmers in the present study. In Rajasthan state, Bikaner district holds highest numbers of clusters i.e., 475 formed for PKVY but Sri Ganganagar district was purposively selected. It needs to be addressed that whether organic farming is profitable or not in this area where chemicals are used indiscriminately. 200 cluster are there in Sri Ganganagar district. Sri Ganganagar district comprises of nine *tehsils* out of which, four *tehsils* namely Sri Vijaynagar, Anupgarh, Raisinghnagar and Sadulshahar were selected randomly for the present investigation. Two *gram panchayats* were selected randomly from each *tehsil* for the present investigation. Thus, total eight *gram panchayats* were selected. From each gram panchayat 10 beneficiary farmers were selected randomly and 10 non-beneficiary farmers were selected from nearby farmers growing same crops in inorganic way. Thus, total 160 respondents i.e., 80 beneficiaries of PKVY and 80 non-beneficiary farmers were selected for the study.

The secondary data were collected from the official website of PKVY, PGS portal of India and Agricultural Department, Sri Ganganagar. The primary data were collected through the personal interview method. The researcher collected data, and the same was recorded on a schedule during the field study. A pre-structured schedule validated after four expert's opinion and pilot survey was used before collecting data. A pilot survey of 20 farmers of the nearby area was done. As only two crops, namely moong bean and wheat crop, were produced organically under the PKVY scheme in the study area, these two crops were studied.

Cost of cultivation was calculated taking variable cost only, as this analysis is done to see the impact of organic farming on cost and returns. Variable cost items included value of hired human labour, value of owned and hired bullock labour, value of owned and hired machine labour, value of owned and purchased seed, value of owned and purchased manures, value of fertilisers and pesticides, irrigation charges, interest on the value of owned capital assets (excluding land) and other miscellaneous expenses.

Gross income and net income were calculated using the following formula:

Gross Income: Synonymous with value of output (both main and by-products).

$$GI = (P_m \times Q_m) + (P_b \times Q_b)$$

Where,

GI= Gross income,

P_m= Price of main product

Q_m= Quantity of main product

P_b= Price of by product

Q_b= Quantity of by product

Net Income: Gross Income – Cost of cultivation

Result and Discussion

The analysis was done separately for two crops under organic cultivation viz., *moong* bean and wheat to fulfil the mentioned objectives. Use of inputs by beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries of PKVY

There were a variety of inputs used by beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries of PKVY. Beneficiary farmers were a little more benefitted as they received inputs at subsidiary prices. Different inputs used by farmers of both categories are given in table 1. From the table, it can be understood that non-beneficiary farmers rely on inorganic fertilisers and plant protection chemicals whereas beneficiary farmers have diversity in input use. They use rhizobium, azotobacter culture

and tricho powder for seed dressing. For fertilisers requirements, they relied on-farm inputs like FYM, vermi-compost and homemade complex mixture and liquid bio-fertilisers like KMB, PSB which are made available by agriculture supervisors of their gram panchayat. Many farmers also used a mixture of jaggery, gram flour and water with irrigation water as this mixture makes a thin layer on soil and helps in conserving moisture for a longer period. The homemade complex mixture includes *jivamrit* and *panchamrit*. For this, beneficiary farmers used to decompose kitchen waste material, leaves of *neem*, *oak*, *datura*, *karanja* with buttermilk and cow urine in a container for 30 to 40 days. During this period, this mixture was daily stirred and is ready to use after removing solid material. For making *panchamrit*, all the five elements, which they received from cows, were mixed by beneficiary farmers, and were used for seed dressing and also with the decomposed mixture. Similar pattern of inputs used by organic farmers were also reported in earlier findings of Phukan *et al.* (2017), Kanagasabapathi and Sakthivel (2019), and Amarnath and Sridhar (2012).

Table 1: Inputs used by beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers

S.No.	Beneficiary farmers	Non-beneficiary farmers
1	Organic seed	Inorganic seed
2	Seed treatment bio-chemicals a) Rhizobium culture b) Azotobactor culture c) Tricho powder d) Homemade mixture by using cow urine, dung, leaves of oak, Neem etc.	Seed treatment chemicals a) Captan b) Thiram c) Carbendazim d) Vitavax e) Imidacloprid
3	Fertilizers a) Farm yard manure (FYM) b) PSB c) KMB d) Vermicompost e) Homemade mixture by using waste decomposer	Fertilizers a) Urea b) DAP c) SSP d) MOP e) NPK f) Sulphur and others
4	Plant Protection Chemicals No chemical used except decomposed liquid spray of natural elements	Plant protection Chemicals a) Monocil b) Corozen c) Ektara d) Curcran e) Confidor f) Proclaim g) Tropicconazole h) Herbicides

Difference in cost of cultivation

Input wise expenditure on *moong* bean cultivation incurred by the beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers is given in table 2. Quantitatively difference in the cost of inputs for the beneficiary farmers and non-beneficiary farmers was observed and the independent sample t-test also shows that the mean difference is highly significant in most of the inputs except irrigation charges. There was a highly significant difference in the total input cost for the beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers, $t(160) = 5.228$, $p < 0.01$. From the table

Table 2: Input cost incurred for *moong* bean crop

S.No.	Items	PKVY Beneficiary	Non-Beneficiary	t-value for equality of means	p value
1	Seed Cost	2746.87	2090.62	5.618	.000**
2	Seed Treatment Cost	75.06	13.12	6.275	.000**
3	FYM	4596.24	1709.99	7.483	.000**
4	Fertilisers	0	1915.87	-8.881	.000**

2, it can be depicted that there is a higher cost incurred for seed (₹ 2746.87) and FYM (₹ 4596.24) for beneficiary farmers as compared to non-beneficiary farmers. PKVY beneficiaries use bio-fertilizers and Bio-chemicals to enhance crop productivity on which they invest ₹ 3359.73 whereas the cost of inorganic fertilisers and plant protection chemicals used by non-beneficiaries of PKVY was ₹ 3544.61. The total cost of input used for the *moong* bean crop is higher in the case of beneficiary farmers (₹ 12480.64) as compared to non-beneficiary farmers (₹9008.57).

5	Bio-fertilisers	1542.73	0	9.678	0.00**
6	Plant protection Chemicals	0	1628.74	-14.355	.000**
7	Bio-Chemicals	1817	0	8.332	.000**
8	Irrigation Charge	1142.5	1257.5	-567	0.572
9	Interest on owned capital assets (6 Months)	560.24	392.72	5.149	.000**
10	Total input cost	12480.60	9008.57	5.228	.000**

** indicate significance at 1% level of probability

Labour cost incurred in the *moong* bean crop for all operations carried out during the crop period by the beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers are given in the table 3. Quantitatively difference in the labour cost for the beneficiary farmers and non-beneficiary farmers was observed and the independent sample t-test also shows that the mean difference is highly significant in most of the labour operation except fertilizer application cost, harvesting

cost and total labour cost. There was highly significant difference in the total cost of cultivation for the beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers, $t(160) = 3.795$, $p < 0.01$. The cost of machine labour and

human labour in the case of beneficiary farmers was ₹ 6981.25 and ₹ 7056.87 respectively whereas non-beneficiary farmers incurred higher machine labour costs (₹ 7835.00) and slightly lower human labour costs (₹ 6635.62). The total labour cost in the moong bean crop incurred by beneficiary farmers was ₹ 14038.12 which was slightly lower as compared to labour cost incurred by non-beneficiary farmers i.e., ₹ 14470.62. Therefore, the total cost of cultivation incurred by the beneficiary farmer was ₹ 26518.76 and by non-beneficiary farmers was ₹ 23479.19 for the same.

Table 4: Total cost of moong bean

S. No.	Items	Beneficiary farmers	Non-beneficiary farmers
1	Input cost	12480.6	9008.57
2	Labour cost	14038.12	14470.62
3	Total cost of cultivation	26518.76	23479.19

Input cost of wheat crop

Input wise expenditure on wheat cultivation incurred by the beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers are given in table 5. Quantitatively difference in the cost of inputs for the beneficiary farmers and non-beneficiary farmers was observed and the independent sample t-test also shows that the mean difference is highly significant in the inputs except seed cost, irrigation charges and interest on owned capital assets. There was highly significant

difference in the total input cost for the beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers, $t(160) = -3.772$, $p < 0.01$.

From the table 5, it can be understood that there is a higher cost incurred for seed (₹ 2648.50), fertilisers (₹ 5707.12) and plant protection chemicals (₹ 2121.53) for non-beneficiary farmers as compared to beneficiary farmers PKVY beneficiaries use bio-fertilisers and bio-chemicals to enhance crop productivity on which they invest ₹ 1662.37 and ₹ 1407.12, respectively.

Table 5: Input cost of wheat crop

S.NO.	Items	PKVY Beneficiary	Non-Beneficiary	t-value for equality of means	p-value
1	Seed Cost	2441.25	2648.50	-1.509	1.34
2	Seed Treatment Cost	275	462.62	-2874	.005**
3	FYM	4317.5	958.75	13957	.000**
4	Fertilisers	0	5707.12	-32.187	.000**
5	Bio Fertilisers	1662.37	0	10.407	.000**
6	Plant Protection Chemical	0	2121.53	-12.327	.000**
7	Bio-chemicals	1407.96	0	-19.639	.000**
8	Irrigation Charge	998.75	1257.5	-1.306	.194
9	Interest on owned capital assets (6 Months)	560.24	392.72	1.062	.290
10	Total input cost	11662.24	13548.75	-3.772	.000**

** indicate significance at 1% level of probability

The cost of FYM was ₹ 4317.50 for beneficiary farmers whereas non-beneficiary farmers use very low amount of FYM and invest only ₹ 958.75 on FYM. The total cost of input used for the wheat crop is less in the case of beneficiary farmers (₹ 11662.24) as compared to non-beneficiary farmers (₹ 13548.75).

Labour cost of wheat crop

Labour cost incurred in the wheat crop for all operations carried out during the crop period by the beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers are given in the table 6. Quantitatively difference in the labour cost for the beneficiary farmers and non-beneficiary farmers was observed and the independent sample t-test also shows that the mean difference is highly significant in most of the labour operations except field preparation cost, sowing cost and fertiliser application cost. There was a significant difference in the total labour cost for the beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers, $t(160) = -2.478$, $p < 0.05$. And total cost of cultivation was also found to be significant, $t(160) = -4.463$, $p < 0.01$. The cost of machine labour and human labour in the case of beneficiary farmers was ₹ 8162.50 and ₹ 8643.50 respectively. Whereas non-beneficiary farmers had

both higher machine labour and human labour costs, ₹ 8332.50 and ₹ 9509.37 respectively. The total labour cost of the wheat crop incurred by beneficiary farmers was ₹ 16806.00 which was lower as compared to labour cost incurred by non-beneficiary farmers i.e., ₹ 17841.87. Therefore, the total cost of cultivation incurred by the beneficiary farmer was ₹ 28468.24 and by non-beneficiary farmers was ₹ 31390.63 for the same as shown in table 7.

In a similar study conducted by Kondaguri *et al.* (2014) on organic vs inorganic paddy cultivation, the average cost of cultivation per acre of paddy on organic farms was ₹ 28585.61 as against ₹ 31697.15 on inorganic farms.

Table 3: Labour cost of moong bean crop

S.No.	Farm Operations	Cost (₹/ha)						t value for equality of mean	p value
		Beneficiary farmers		Total	Non-beneficiary farmers		Total		
		Machine Labour	Human Labour		Machine Labour	Human Labour			
1	Field Preparation	1809.37	353.75	2163.12	1988.75	466.25	2455	-2.028	.044*
2	Manuring	0	1718.75	1718.75	0	602.5	602.5	8.950	.000**
3	sowing cost	855	370	1225	871.25	482.5	1353.75	-2.710	.007**
4	Fertilizer Application Cost	0	750	750	0	750	750	0.000	1.000
5	Weeding and Hoeing	493.12	1230	1723.12	595	1542.5	2137.5	-3.463	.001**
6	Chemical Application Cost	413.75	851.25	1265	758.75	940	1698.75	-4.670	.000**
7	Transportation Cost	1567.5	289.37	1856.87	1756.25	311.87	2068.12	-2.345	.020*
8	Harvesting Cost	1842.5	1493.75	3336.25	1865	1540	3405	-3.49	.727
9	Total Labour Cost	6981.25	7056.87	14038.12	7835	6635.62	14470.62	-1.234	.219

** and * indicate significance at 1 % and 5% level probability

Table 6: Labour cost of wheat crop

S.No.	Farm Operations	Cost (₹/ha)						t-value for equality of mean	p-value
		Beneficiary Farmers		Total	Non-beneficiary Farmers		Total		
		Machine Labour	Human Labour		Machine Labour	Human Labour			
1	Field Preparation	1987.5	383.75	2371.25	1988.75	466.25	2455	-561	
2	Manuring	0	1808.75	1808.75	0	702.5	702.5	7.183**	
3	sowing cost	896.25	403.75	1300	871.25	477.5	1348.75	-.951	
4	Fertilizer Application Cost	0	792.5	792.5	0	750	750	.535	
5	Weeding and Hoeing	0	615.62	615.62	0	0	0	5.935**	
6	Chemical Application Cost	403.75	881.25	1285	758.75	940	1698.75	-4.711**	
7	Transportation Cost	1527.5	285.625	1813.12	1756.25	311.875	2068.12	-2.765**	
8	Harvesting Cost	3347.5	3472.25	6819.75	2957.5	5861.25	8818.75	-7.487**	
9	Total Labour Cost	8162.50	8643.50	16806.00	8332.50	9509.37	17841.87	-2.478*	

** and * indicate significance at 5% and 1% level of probability

Table: 7. Total coat of wheat crop

S. No.	Items	Beneficiary farmers	Non-beneficiary farmers	(₹/ha)
1	Input cost	11662.24	13548.75	
2	Labour cost	16806.00	17841.87	
3	Total cost of cultivation	28468.24	31390.63	

Difference in gross and net returns

The results of yield and gross returns of moong bean crop for beneficiary and non-beneficiary of PKVY are presented in table 8. Quantitatively difference in the returns of moong bean crop for the beneficiary farmers and non-beneficiary farmers was observed and the independent sample t-test also shows that the mean difference is highly significant. There was a significant difference in the total economic profit for the beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers, $t(160) = -3.732$, $p < 0.01$. The table shows that the total yield of the main product was 8.59 q/ha and 10.85 q/ha for the beneficiary and non-beneficiary

farmers. And the total yield of the by-product was 8.56 q/ha and 9.87 q/ha for the beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers. Beneficiary farmers earn a gross return of ₹ 64938.50 and ₹ 38419.69 as economic profit whereas non-beneficiary farmers earn a gross return of ₹ 77092.62 and ₹ 53613.40 as net profit. The benefit-cost ratio (BCR) of beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries of PKVY growing moong bean crop shows that it was 1.44 and 2.28, respectively. BCR of the non-beneficiary farmers was high because the productivity of moong bean of some sample farmers was high and also, they had a lower total cost of cultivation.

Table 8: Gross and net returns in moong bean crop

S.No.	Particulars	PKVY Beneficiary	Non-Beneficiary	t-value for equality of means	p-value
1	Total Production (q/ha)	8.59	10.85	-4.605	.000**
2	Main product Price (₹/q)	7347.5	6936.25	2.118	.037*
3	Total By-Product Yield (q/ha)	8.56	9.87	-2.568	.011*
4	By Product Price (₹/q)	155	144.87	2.019	.046*
5	Total Returns (₹/ha)	64938.59	77092.62	-3.003	.003**
6	Net Profit over variable cost (₹/ha)	38419.69	53613.40	-3.732	.000**
7	Total cost of Cultivation (₹/ha)	26518.76	23479.19	3.795	.000**
8	Benefit-cost ratio (BCR)	1.44	2.28		

** and * indicate significance at 5 % and 1% level of probability

The results of yield and gross returns of the wheat crop for beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries of PKVY are presented in Table 9. Quantitatively difference in the returns of wheat crop for the beneficiary farmers and non-beneficiary farmers was observed and the independent sample t-test also shows that the mean difference is highly significant for the total production. But there was a non-significant difference in the total economic profit for the beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers, $t(160) = 1.514$, $p > 0.05$. The table shows that the total yield of the main product was 33.8 q/ha and 47.66 q/ha for the beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers respectively. The total yield of the by-product was 36.36 q/ha and 51.63 q/ha for the beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers respectively. Beneficiary farmers earned a gross return of ₹111570.00 and ₹ 83101.75 as net profit over variable cost whereas non-beneficiary farmers earn a gross return of

₹109273.56 and ₹ 77882.93 as net profit. The benefit-cost ratio (BCR) of beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries of PKVY growing wheat crop as shown in table 4.17, it was 2.94 and 2.49, respectively. BCR of the beneficiary farmers was high because the productivity of wheat of some sample farmers was high and also, they had a lower total cost of cultivation. In a similar study conducted by Kondaguri *et al.* (2014) on organic vs inorganic paddy cultivation, the net return on the organic paddy farm was ₹ 21256.70 and was ₹ 15643.29 on inorganic farms, the BC ratio was higher on organic farms (1.74) when compared to inorganic farms (1.49). A similar study carried out by Suwanmaneepong *et al.* (2020) reveals that the cost of production was higher, and output was lower under organic rice farming. Despite this, organic rice farming was more profitable than conventional farming due to the higher prevailing market price for organic rice.

Table 9: Gross and net returns in wheat crop

S.No.	Particulars	PKVY Beneficiary	Non-Beneficiary	t-value for equality of means	p-value
1	Total Production (q/ha)	33.80	47.66	-11.046	.000**
2	Main product Price (₹/q)	2938.53	1924.038	12.955	.000**
3	Total By-Product Yield (q/ha)	36.36	51.63	- 6.766	.000**
4	By Product Price (₹/q)	336.81	340.23	- 0.790	.431
5	Total Returns (₹/ha)	111570.00	109273.56	0.697	.487
6	Net profit over variable cost (₹/ha)	83101.75	77882.93	1.514	.132
7	Total cost of Cultivation	28468.24	31390.63	-4.463	.000**
8.	Benefit-cost ratio (BCR)	2.94	2.49		

** indicate significance at 1% level of probability

Difference in marketing channels to sell the outputs and price of outputs For marketing of Produce most of beneficiary farmers sell their produce directly to consumers in their locale area whereas all non-beneficiary farmers were selling their produce in APMC markets.

73.75 per cent beneficiary farmers were selling *moong* bean directly to consumers at price ₹ 7677.96 per quintal. And 90 per cent beneficiary farmers were selling wheat directly to consumer at ₹ 3101.38 per quintal.

Table: 10. Marketing channels followed by sample farmers

S. No.	Marketing Channel	Beneficiary Farmers		Non-beneficiary farmers	
		Total	Price (₹/q)	Total	Price (₹/q)
A.	Moong bean				
1.	Consumer	59 (73.75)	7677.96	0	
2.	APMC market	21 (26.25)	6419.04	80 (100)	6936.25
B.	Wheat				
1.	Consumer	72 (90.00)	3101.38	0	
2.	APMC market	8 (10.00)	1931.25	80 (100)	1924.03

*Figures in parentheses indicate percentage of total

Conclusions

The total production, returns and cost of cultivation are significantly different for beneficiary farmers who are producing crop organically and those who are not producing organically.

Total cost of cultivation of the moong bean crop was high for beneficiary farmers while it was lower for beneficiary farmers in production of wheat crop.

Benefit-cost ratio (BCR) of the moong bean crop for beneficiary farmers was 1.44 which was found lower as compared to BCR of non-beneficiary farmers i.e., 2.28. The benefit-cost ratio (BCR) of the wheat crop for beneficiary farmers was 2.94 which was found higher as compared to BCR of non-beneficiary farmers i.e., 2.49.

There is low profit of organic moong bean crop for beneficiary farmer due to marketing and price constraints. Most of the organic produce was sold to nearby consumers directly.

Beneficiary farmers of PKVY are not getting all the mentioned benefits of this scheme as they are unable to sell their produce in distant market and receive low price for their organic produce.

References

1. Amarnath, J. S. and Sridhar, V. (2012) An economic analysis of organic farming in Tamil Nadu, India. *Bangladesh Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 35(1/2), 33-51.
2. Committee on Estimates (2015-16) "National Project on Organic Farming," Ministry of Agriculture, (Department of Agriculture & Cooperation) Ninth Report, Sixteenth Lok Sabha, New Delhi: Government Press.
3. Gopinath, K. A., Kumari, V. V., Sowjanya, J., Bhargavi, B., Rajkumar, B., Sunitha, B., Lavanaya, N. and Singh, V. K. (2025) Organic farming in rainfed areas of India: A review. *Indian Journal of Agronomy*, 70, 11-19.
4. Kanagaspathi, K. and Sakthivel, V. (2019) An Analysis of Adoption of Organic Farming Practices of Tribal Farmers of Kolli Hills. *Journal of Plant Archives*. 19(2), 3533-3534.
5. Kondaguri, R. H., Kunnal, L. B., Patil, B. L., Handigol, J. A. and Doddamani, M. T. (2014) Comparative economics of organic and inorganic rice farming in Tungabhadra command area of Karnataka. *Karnataka Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 27(4), 476-480.
6. Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation (2021), *Statistics Times*, <https://statisticstimes.com/economy/country/india-gdp-sectorwise.php>

7. Phukan, P., Lepcha, B. and Avasthe, R. (2017) Impact of Training Programmes on Adoption of Organic Farming Practices with Organic Marketing in East Sikkim. *Indian Research Journal of Extension Education*, 17(4), 112-116.
8. Plecher, H. (2020) Distribution of the workforce across economic sectors in India 2020. *Statista*, <https://www.statista.com/statistics/271320/distribution-of-the-workforce-across-economic-sectors-in>
9. Ranwa, N., Kharkwal, S., Bhinchhar, B. K., Shekhawat, P. S. and Jain, S. (2024) A Comparative Study on Conventional and Organic Barley Cultivation in Jaipur District of Rajasthan.
10. Reganold, J. P. and Wachter, J. M. (2016) Organic agriculture in the twenty-first century. *Nature plants*, 2(2), 1-8.
11. Sharma, A. K., Patel, N., Painuli, D. K. and Mishra, D. (2015) Organic Farming in Low Rainfall Areas. *Central Arid Zone Research Institute*, Jodhpur, 48-58.
12. Singh, H., Sharma, S. K. and Meena, M. K. (2023) Preliminary Study of Organic Farming Practices in Southern Rajasthan, India. *Asian Journal of Agricultural Extension, Economics & Sociology*, 41(12), 364-371.
13. Suwanmaneepong, S., Kerdsriserm, C., Lepcha, N., Cavite, H. J. and Llonas, C. A. (2020) Cost and return analysis of organic and conventional rice production in Chachoengsao Province, Thailand. *Organic Agriculture*, 1-10.